

ELIXIR Scientific Programme 2024-2028

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ELIXIR Italy All hands
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www.elixir-europe.org

A sustainable infrastructure for biological data

ELIXIR Members

ELIXIR Observers

ELIXIR's funding model

Node funding:

- National roadmap funding
- Competitive research grants
- EU Structural Funds or Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)
- Trusts and foundations
- Industry collaboration

<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/sustainability-plan>

ELIXIR's key stakeholders

ELIXIR Nodes

24 ELIXIR Nodes
250+ institutes
850+ scientists

Users

Bioinformaticians
500,000+ life science researchers
Users in industry

Funders & decision makers

European Union
National funding agencies
ESFRI delegates
ELIXIR Board members

Collaborators

ESFRI RIs
Global initiatives (GA4GH)
National initiatives (Australian
BioCommons, NIH)

How we work

ELIXIR brings together **groups of experts** from different **technological areas, scientific domains** and **ELIXIR Nodes**

Cutting edge **internal projects** are funded to further encourage collaborations

Technical and training coordinators based in the Nodes support different groups of experts to work together

Platforms

The five ELIXIR Platforms develop and coordinate cross-domain services across ELIXIR.

Communities

ELIXIR Communities work in a particular life science domain and give feedback on the Platform services.

Focus Groups

Focus Groups are informal groups that look at emerging areas of interest in life science. Most are open to non-ELIXIR members.

Internal projects

Internal projects fund the Platforms and Communities to develop resources, and encourage collaboration across the Nodes.

Coordinators

Technical and Training Coordinators advise the Platforms and promote collaboration between the Platforms and the Nodes.

Evolution of Scientific Programmes

2014-2018

EUR ~18 million

2019-2023

EUR ~36 million

2024-2028

EUR ~41 million

Developing the Programme - consultation process

ELIXIR Scientific Programme guides all our activities

Implemented through:

- Commissioned Services
- EC Projects

ELIXIR Commissioned Services

Commissioned Services are technical projects that guide future service development, drive standards adoption and connect ELIXIR Nodes

Building a single infrastructure by connecting Europe

- Over **120 projects** supported by **EUR 26 million**
- Improving **collaboration between ELIXIR Nodes**
- **Connecting, integrating and sustaining** life science data resources
- **Developing and improving services** used by life scientists globally

ELIXIR's EC funded projects - examples

- ELIXIR coordinates and partners in many EC funded projects
- Nodes provide data management expertise and infrastructure
- ELIXIR is key life science element of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

European Genomic Data Infrastructure	GDI	Providing access to genomic data to improve research, policy making and healthcare
BY-COVID	BY-COVID	Making COVID-19 and infectious disease data accessible to all
eosoc cancer	EOSC4Cancer	Accelerating data driven cancer research
Biodiversity Genomics Europe	BGE	Reversing biodiversity loss through genomics research

ELIXIR's Purpose, Identity and Values

Purpose

Together we accelerate the understanding of life

Identity

We enable scientists to access and analyse life science data

Values

1. We work to benefit everyone
2. We are trusted
3. We work with a spirit of openness
4. We strive for excellence
5. We work in an environment of respect

ELIXIR: Together we accelerate the understanding of life

Deeply rooted collaborations

Purposeful and trust-based transnational collaborations on key European projects and prioritised initiatives

Enabling scientific breakthroughs

Fostering breakthroughs through the re-use of very large and complex datasets

Connected, accessible data and tools

Extensive and equitable cross-disciplinary data access through coordinated research data management

Major challenges for Europe - and the world

ELIXIR enables scientists to access and analyse life science data

ELIXIR enables scientists to access and analyse life science data

24-28 Programme - Strategic tiers and Programme Priorities

Strategic tiers

2024-2028 Programme Priorities

1. Enable scientists to access and analyse life science data

2. Deliver services to support federated data management and analytics

3. Equip national Nodes for successful long-term operations

4. Develop people and capacity to benefit science and society

24-28 Programme - Scientific themes

Cellular and molecular
research

Biodiversity, food security
and pathogens

Human data and
translational research

Scientific priorities and technical focus areas

Scientific

Technical

**Cellular & molecular
research**

**Biodiversity, food
security & pathogens**

**Human data and
translational research**

Science - Focussing on High Priority Communities

1. Enable scientists to access and analyse life science data

2. Deliver services to support federated data management and analytics

3. Equip national Nodes for successful long-term operations

4. Develop people and capacity to benefit science and society

1.1

Cellular & molecular research

1.2

Biodiversity, food security, pathogens

1.3

Human data and translational research

Detailed Ambitions - Science

1.1 Cellular and molecular research

Connect the latest developments and established data resources to realise the potential of cellular and molecular biology

1.2 Biodiversity, food security, pathogens

Mobilise and integrate molecular data to support transnational research programmes in biodiversity, food security and infectious disease

1.3 Human data and translational research

Provide the infrastructure to support the discovery, access, sharing and analysis of human genomics data and linked phenotypic/other data on a massive scale

Technology: Building on the strength of our Platforms

1. Enable scientists to access and analyse life science data

2. Deliver services to support federated data management and analytics

3. Equip national Nodes for successful long-term operations

4. Develop people and capacity to benefit science and society

2.1 Research data management & knowledge sharing

2.2 Reproducible analytics & infrastructure

2.3 Federated service delivery

Detailed Ambitions - Technology

2.1 Research data management & knowledge sharing

Provide data and knowledge management infrastructure to support open, data-driven research in the life sciences

2.2 Reproducible analytics & infrastructure

Develop our infrastructure to enable end-to-end management of life science software, workflows and containers

2.3 Federated service delivery

Develop a federated pan-European technical infrastructure for life scientists to access data, storage and compute services

Nodes and people are the foundation of ELIXIR

ELIXIR is driven from
the Node level up

Nodes - Making the federated infrastructure a reality

1. Enable scientists to access and analyse life science data

2. Deliver services to support federated data management and analytics

3. Equip national Nodes for successful long-term operations

4. Develop people and capacity to benefit science and society

3.1

Node operations

3.2

National research & open science policy

3.3

Industry & innovation

3.4

Impact and long-term sustainability

Detailed Ambitions - Nodes

3.1 Nodes operations

Nodes have the operational capabilities to contribute to a European infrastructure for data

3.2 National research & open science policy

Nodes are aligned with national research priorities and open science policies

3.3 Industry & innovation

Nodes are fundamental to national industry ecosystems and engage in EU-wide industry efforts

3.4 Impact & long-term sustainability

Nodes are empowered and supported in their efforts towards long-term sustainability

People: Critical for ELIXIR's success

1. Enable scientists to access and analyse life science data

2. Deliver services to support federated data management and analytics

3. Equip national Nodes for successful long-term operations

4. Develop people and capacity to benefit science and society

4.1

Users of ELIXIR services

4.2
staff

Management & operational

4.3

Technical & scientific staff

4.4

A diverse & well-connected
people network

Detailed Ambitions - People

4.1

Users of ELIXIR services

All users of ELIXIR services have access to training, resources and expertise

4.2

Management & operational staff

Nodes are well equipped to efficiently manage and run a distributed infrastructure

4.3

Technical & scientific staff

ELIXIR technical and scientific staff have the skills needed for operational excellence and impact

4.4

A diverse & well-connected people network

ELIXIR is a diverse network of people who are appropriately credited for their work

Science

- 3 Commissioned Services proposed, 2024-2026
- Start: 1 January 2024

Technology

- 5 Commissioned Services proposed, 2024-2026
- Start: 1 January 2024
- 1 Commissioned Service in preparation

Nodes

- 1 Commissioned Service in preparation

People

- 2 Commissioned Services in preparation
- Capacity Building and Knowledge Exchange Programme - call to be opened in January 2024

Staff exchanges

Staff Exchange Programme

The [Staff Exchange Programme](#) funds projects that:

Support the professional
development of Node
members

Fund staff exchange across the
Nodes

Support interactions between
academia and industry

Connect and stay up to date

@ELIXIREurope

Twitter/ X

Follow us on Twitter/X for daily updates of upcoming ELIXIR events and ELIXIR-related research outcomes.

ELIXIR Europe

YouTube

Follow our YouTube channel for recordings of ELIXIR webinars and workshops.

company/elixir-europe

LinkedIn

Follow our LinkedIn for event informations and new job vacancies in ELIXIR Hub.

<https://elixir-europe.org/events>

Webinars & events

Check out ELIXIR's event page for upcoming webinars and events.

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